

Aesthetic Excellence through Digital Smile Designing: Transforming Anterior Rehabilitation

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Abstract

Introduction: "Quacks" refers to defective prostheses, and repairing them is never easy for a prosthodontist. supplying permanent prosthodontic restorations that adhere to the It can be difficult to meet the functional and aesthetic needs of patients. particularly in the maxilla anteriorly. The choice of a suitable treatment necessitates a thorough assessment and methodical planning. Case Report: It addresses how to manage a case's aesthetics using Mandibular and maxillary anterior with a defective, large prosthesis, It resulted in "QUACK" due to inflammation and poor aesthetics. "Prosthesis."

In conclusion, each aesthetic adjustment calls for the right abilities and understanding. A number of factors need to be considered. Taking into account such management in order to recover the lost essence of beauty.

Introduction:

A person's greatest beauty asset is their smile. One of the most important facial expressions for showing friendliness, agreement, and gratitude is a smile. In addition to being necessary from a functional standpoint, teeth also play a significant role in a person's psychological wellbeing.¹ Furthermore, dental diseases, trauma, and heredity are the main causes of the catastrophic event of aesthetic tooth loss in younger individuals. Any of the aforementioned causes of tooth loss not only affects the patient's social welfare but also their ability to perform. The lack or misaligned front teeth not only compromises appearance but also has an impact on phonetics, food cutting, and—most importantly—the anterior guiding, which is essential for safeguarding posterior teeth.

Achieving a harmonious balance between functionality and aesthetics poses a significant challenge for prosthodontists, that provides treatment planning according to knowledge of prosthetic limitation and aesthetic outcomes. The concept of Digital Smile Design (DSD) aims to assist clinicians by enhancing the visual representation of a patient's aesthetic concerns. By providing a clear understanding of potential solutions, it educates and motivates patients about the benefits of treatment, ultimately increasing case acceptance. Digital Smile Design (DSD) is a digital tool that enables the creation and projection of a new smile design by generating simulations and pre-visualizations of the anticipated results of a proposed treatment.²

This case report describes the management of patient with spacing and flared upper anterior and missing with missing centrals and laterals in lower arch through digital smile design tool.

CASE REPORT

A 24-year female patient reported to department of prosthodontics with chief complaint of spacing in upper anterior and missing with lower anterior and wants aesthetic correction within a 2 months. [fig 1]. The medical history of the patients was non-contributory to the contraindication of dental treatment. On intraoral examination loss of lower anterior was due to aggressive periodontitis and spacing with maxillary anterior due to mouth breathing habit. [fig 2]. Thus, treatment plan decided was diagnostic mock up followed by digital smile design.

Fig1: pre-operative view showing flared upper anterior and lower missing anterior

Upper lower intra oral occlusal view

Clinical procedure: Diagnostic impression was made of upper and lower arches by irreversible hydrocolloid impression material (Align gum; [fig3]

(fig 3) Diagnostic impression

Prime Chrome Alginate Impression Material) and cast poured with type IV dental stone (kalabhai ultra stone dental stone). Diagnostic cast were mounted for diagnostic mock up and wax up was done to visualise better outcome. [fig4].

fig4) Diagnostic wax-up

Diagnostic mounting and extra oral photographs were sent for digital smile designing and 3D printing model was made. [fig5]

Printed model of diagnostic mock up was shown to patient.

Fig 5 (printed model)

After planning it was decided that Intentional root canal treatment was advised with 11,21,22 in maxillary arch and 32,42. Minimal Tooth preparation was done and Temporisation was done with self-cure [Prevest DenPro Ora Temp C&B Crown & Bridge Polishers] for 15 days. [fig6]

figure: 6 Temporisation

Final preparations were done followed by retraction cord placement [prime ultrafine retraction cord 000] and final impression with addition silicon elastomeric impression [zhernack] [fig7]

Final impression with addition silicone

Shade selection was done using vita shade guide [VITA classical A1–D4® shade guide with VITA Bleached Shade.

Bisque trial of upper lower anterior and minor corrections was done. [fig 8]

Final view

Final cementation was done with RM-GIC [Prevest Fusion Ultra D/C- Intro Pack dual cure resin based luting cement] [fig 8]

Final cementation

Front view

lateral view

DISCUSSION

In modern dentistry, the significance of aesthetics has grown significantly. Patients often seek dental care driven by their desire for aesthetic improvement, influenced by cultural, ethnic, and personal preferences. While the restoration of a natural appearance for edentulous patients is frequently discussed, it's commonly misunderstood. Achieving dental aesthetics requires deliberate planning and skilful execution, aiming to create an appealing smile that enhances an individual's societal acceptance. Digital smile design, a multipurpose conceptual tool that can facilitate careful examination of the patient's facial and dental features that may have been missed by clinical, photographic, or diagnostic cast-based evaluation procedures as proposed by Coachman and Calamita. This can support diagnostic vision, enhance communication, and improve treatment predictability. It has progressively evolved from physical to digital designs and has also advanced from 2D to 3D.³

The advantage of digital smile design is that therapy predictability is increased when patients may see the anticipated outcome before the actual course of therapy begins, thanks to digital

imaging and design. By providing patients with a graphical representation of the outcome, the practitioner can allay their fears and educate and inspire them about the advantages of the treatment.⁴ Through the artistic visualisation of patients' problems through digital analysis of facial, gingival, and dental parameters that will analyse the smile and the face in an objective and standardised manner, it improves clinician diagnosis and treatment planning.⁵ It enhances communication not just between the doctor and the patient but also among members of the interdisciplinary team, between the doctor and the lab technician. The main determinants of aesthetic correction which are to be considered while rehabilitating anterior are:

- Aesthetics
- Phonetics
- Positional relationships of the maxillary and mandibular anterior teeth.
- Proportion (golden proportion).

Conclusion:

In this case patient was not willing for orthodontic treatment as there was waiting period of 1.5- 2 years, so we have suggested the prosthetic rehabilitation of anterior as she was concerned about aesthetics. Digital smile designing was option suggested and she got agreed. Treatment objectives were achieved by accurate diagnosis, meticulous treatment planning together with digital smile designing dedicated team approach involving different disciplines in dentistry.

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